
Research

Analysis and selection of borehole composite length for accurate and optimal geological resource reserve calculation: A case study of timulike iron deposit

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Abstract: Standardizing the length of borehole samples is one of the essential steps in the estimation and calculation of geological resource reserves with contemporary software such as Surpac. This standardization resulting in a composite chain file has a significant impact on the accuracy and optimization of the estimate. Unsuitable composite lengths can lead to underestimating or overestimating these resource reserves. This article helps remedy this problem in the case of the Timulike iron deposit in China. The geological data are first processed in Microsoft Excel using standard mathematical computation and the iron content curve to rectify, filter, rearrange, and readjust them in files in the Surpac format. After that, the anomalous results were checked and corrected using the histogram analysis and cumulative frequency of the iron contents. Afterward, 30 composites with lengths ranging from 0.5 meters to 10 meters are constructed using the Surpac software's composite construction approach and data from the study area's sampling lengths as well as lengths that were often employed in previous research. Their statistical results, which are extracted and listed in a table, include variance, mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation. These statistical results can now be represented and interpreted more effectively thanks to the statistical approach of examining the histograms of the data in Microsoft Excel. According to the statistical analysis of these results, three groups of composites are identified: those with short lengths (between 0.5 and 1 meters), those with long lengths (5 and 10 meters), and those with lengths that are very near to the average length of the drill samples (from 1.7 to 2 meters). These results also show that the iron resource reserves will be overestimated by short-length composites and underestimated by long-length composites. On the other hand, composites with lengths that are extremely close to the average length of the samples will result in more accurate estimations. The length of 2 meters was determined to be the composite length best suited to make an optimal estimate and an accurate calculation of the Timulike iron deposit resource reserves through a more thorough investigation of this last group of composites utilizing Microsoft Excel's conditional formatting method.

Keywords: Composites, Length, Timulike, Iron grade, Histogram, Mean, Variance, Standard deviation, Coefficient of variation, estimation, calculation of resource reserves.

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1. Introduction

One of the primary objectives of geological resource exploration and prospecting is discovering, estimating, and calculating the reserves of ore bodies. Today, various techniques and programs are available for estimating these resource reserves, although the geostatistical estimating techniques and Surpac software are among the most used. Due to their high level of accuracy and quick estimation processes, geostatistical approaches are more frequently used [1]. They were developed because it became clear from conventional statistics that it was difficult to accurately estimate the reserves of dispersed minerals [2].

The surpac software uses a block model, a three-dimensional graphic database, to estimate geological resources. The length of the samples is standardized before a block model estimation based on the samples' contents and a geostatistical analysis of the data is performed [3]. As part of this standardization, composite chain files, or chain files containing data on mineral analysis, are extracted from databases [4]. This chain file's composition is based on the frequency of sample lengths taken into account in the laboratory when determining the ore's sought parameters, such as the quantity of the useful element taken into account and its specific density. These samples were extracted from drill cores used for geological exploration. Six categories of composite generation techniques were identified by Sahoo [5] in the Surpac program, including downhole, bank elevation, grade limitations, geological constraints, from the end of the hole, and numerous pieces.

By its definition, it should be noted that the length of the composites has a significant impact on the accuracy of the estimates. A composite length must not only be reflective of the boreholes but also cautious with respect to the original data, according to Lee [6]. The length of 1 meter is frequently used in the estimate of resources using the SURPAC software [2, 6-18]. Other investigations, however, have chosen different composite lengths, including lengths of 5 meters [5], 3 and 3.3 [19, 20], 2 meters [3, 21, 22], 1.5 meters [1, 23], and even less than 1 meter [24, 25]. According to Moharaj [26] the fact that an estimate would be accurate and simple with a large composite length when the mineral distribution is continuous suggests that this length is also influenced by whether the mineral distribution is continuous or discontinuous. The length of 10 meters displayed a higher mean iron content than the other four composite lengths—5 meters, 10 meters, 15 meters, 20 meters, and 40 meters—that they evaluated. Mello [25] determined the length of the composites based on the mode of distribution of the length of the samples before combining samples that had comparable variance, geology, means, and histogram shapes for the purposes of optimizing variography and kriging. Siddiqui [22] created their composite in their case by adding roughly a value of 0.5 meters to the mean of the intervals of variables. Al Mesbah [24] selected the same composite length for the bulk of the drill sampling intervals. In order to maximize their estimation, Nezamolhosseini [20] divided the waste rocks from the ores by producing two composite files. The minimum sample size required for composite generation is also required, and in virtually all instances, 75% of the sample is taken into account [1, 5, 22]. Simply put, this indicates that each sample will return at least 75% of its length during composition.

1.1 Formulation of the problem

The length of the composites is an essential parameter to obtain accurate geological resource estimates in 3D modeling. The effectiveness of the estimate can be significantly impacted by even minor errors in the length selection. These composite lengths, however, differ from study to study and from one particular situation to another. In this study, several composite lengths were examined based on how frequently they were used in previous estimation studies on ore bodies. The statistical results from this analysis will be compared to see which is best. The specific case of the TIMULIKE iron deposit is considered in this research. It is a mineral found in northeast China's Xinjiang area that is now in the exploitation stage. In-depth estimates of the amount of iron ore have been made as a result of advanced geological exploration work on this deposit, and this is one of the recommendations that have been made. This study contributes to the choice of composite length to enhance the accuracy of the estimates and calculations of iron ore reserves.

2.0 Presentation of the study area

The study area is located 46 kilometers northwest of Fuyun in Fuyun County, Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region. Its area is 0.996 square kilometers and its geographical center is located at 89°14'50"E and 47°22'33" N (Beijing 54 coordinate system). The road is the main mode of transport in the mining region. There is a road leading to the mining area and reaching Fuyun County via national roads 216 and 217 which connect Urumqi, Karamay, and other places. The railway network that connects the city of Beitun to the rest of the country, Europe and Asia has also been completed and made available for traffic. Regular civil aviation flights connect Altai, Beitun, and Urumqi for easy transportation (see Figure 1).

Fig. 1: Location map for mining and road traffic of the Timurik iron mine

2.1 Geological Background

The Lowest Devonian Kangbutiebao Formation, which is split into two lithological sections, is represented by the stratum that is exposed in the mining region by the lower subgroup (D1k1) of that formation. The first lithological section (D1k11) is composed primarily of banded biotite gneiss, shallow granule, intercalated with biotite schist, and magnetite granulite, with traces of amphibole plagioclase, amphibole plagioclase, magneto-angle amphibolite, and biotite granulite in its upper part. The second lithological section (D1k12) consists of biotite amphibolite, plagioclase amphibolite, biotite plagiogneiss, porphyritic amphibolite granulite, and marble lens in its lower part, intercalated amphibole gneiss, magnetite gneiss and biotite, tremolite plagioclase gneiss, biotite gneiss, and metagranulites, sandwiching marble and iron ore deposits in its middle part and interbedded schistose sandstone, tufted sandstone, physical-gravel sandstone, intercalated chemicals and a marble lens in its upper part. From a structural point of view, the complex syncline of Metz

on the northeast wing and the Balabac syncline Bulak dominate the area. On this northeast wing, there are also small secondary local folds. Fault structures are not well developed. The acid rocks in the study area have a genetic relationship with iron ore and are mainly composed of biotite granite and biotite plagiogranite. The dyke rocks mainly include pegmatite dykes, and a small amount of small-scale quartz dykes are produced. Volcanic rocks consist of basalt and rhyolite rocks (Daian). Metamorphism in this zone is dominated by regional metamorphism, followed by contact metamorphism, migmatization, and dynamic metamorphism. The relationship between these metamorphisms is complex. Metamorphic minerals include biotite, muscovite, epidote, and cordierite. Migmatization has occurred in the contact zone of the granite outside the mining area and the veins are light-colored granite and pegmatite granite. Contact metamorphism occurred in the southwest contact zone of the granite body. Dynamic metamorphism occurred near the fault structure, resulting in the development of rock fragmentation, foliation, and cleavage. Metamorphic rocks in this area are expected to belong to the greenschist facies group of the low-pressure facies' series.

The iron deposit in the mining area is divided into three (3) circled ore sections with a total of eleven (11) iron ore bodies. The ore bodies contained in the 3 ore sections and their numbers are respectively Fe1 ore section with Fe1 ore body, the Fe2 ore section with Fe2-1, Fe2-2, Fe2-2A ore bodies, Fe2-2B, the Fe3 ore section with the Fe3, Fe3-1, Fe3-1A, Fe3-1B, Fe3-2, Fe3-2A ore bodies. Among them, Fe1, Fe2-1, Fe2-2, Fe2-2B and Fe3 ore bodies are major ore bodies and the rest are smaller-scale ore bodies.

Fig. 2: Topographic and geological map of the Timulike iron deposit.

3.0 Research Methodology

In this study, Surpac software [27-29], was often used in conjunction with other software such as ArcGIS 10.8, and Microsoft Excel 2016.

3.1 Data collection and pre-processing

Data collection and pre-processing consist of extracting data from the results of geological explorations, transcription into Microsoft Excel, verification, filtration, and reinterpretation. This data includes geographic coordinates, strikes, dips, mean iron grades, depths of each drill hole, and others. The data were then quantified, standardized in the geographic coordinate system environment, then structured and sorted in the form of four tables called COLLAR, SURVEY,

and SAMPLE tables. Finally, the geological database needed to analyze the composites' length is created by importing these tables into the Surpac software.

3.2 Composite length construction with several test values

The classification of the grades of the usable minerals in the database, their extraction, and storage in a chain file for the simple study of the law of distribution of the grade, as well as a block interpolation in the sample, and the composition of the samples was carried out in Surpac. The Surpac software provides the following six (6) sample grouping methods: composite by grade (grade-constrained), composite by geology (according to geological constraints), composite by elevation (according to elevation contour lines), composite by downhole (according to exploration engineering), composite from the end of the hole, and multiple elements. For geological statistics, only the composite points produced by downhole and elevation are acceptable. In this study, we make use of a down-the-hole composite that follows exploration engineering standards. For this, the menu to execute in surpac is database > Composite > Downhole. In the dialog box that will be generated, several test values of composite lengths will be used to generate different composites for a minimum percentage of the sample to include 75%. The selection of the test lengths is made base on previous studies carried out by certain authors and based on the length of the exploration samples in the Timulike zone. Composite lengths sectioned for this purpose include:

- Test length no. 1: 1 meter, chosen because it is the most commonly used composite length [2, 6-18];
- Length test n°2: mean value of the lengths of samples in the exploration drill holes of the Timulike deposit;
- Test length n°3: 1.5 meters, chosen because it is also often used in the estimation of reserve resources [1, 23];
- Test length n°4: addition of 0.5 meters to the mean value of the sample lengths in the exploration drill holes of the Timulike deposit [22];
- Test length no. 5: 10 meters, suggested by Moharaj [26] after studies carried out on the length of composites.
- The other test values derive from the tightening or widening of the amplitude around these first five (5) values according to the approximation of their statistical result to those of the real values.

After the construction of the composites according to these different test lengths, a statistical report of each composite will be generated and the values of the mean of the contents, the standard deviation, the variance, and the coefficient of variation of the different composites will serve as a performance indicator to deduce which statistical report is closest to that of the real data.

3.3 Statistical analysis of the data of each composite.

After the creation of the database and the construction of the test composites, another analysis of the data is necessary. This analysis will make it possible to eliminate the last errors and incorrect values in the tables and consequently improve the consistency of the data. Additionally, it will allow for the quick determination of each composite's mean, standard deviation, variance, and coefficient of variation—which serve as markers for the analysis of composites' lengths. For this, the Histogram and Cumulative Frequency analysis techniques will be employed.

3.3.1 Data Histogram Method

In descriptive statistics, the histogram consists in representing the numbers of classes by contiguous rectangles whose surface represents the number or the area a_j . For a frequency histogram, the height of the rectangle corresponding to class j is therefore given by:

$$h_j = \frac{n_j}{a_j}$$

Where h_j is the workforce density; n_j designates the number corresponding to the value j or the j class. For a value j of a discrete quantitative variable corresponds to an effective. The frequency of a modality or a distinct value designates

the number of times that this distinct value appears; a_j is the area of the histogram. It can be calculated according to the formula

$$f_j = \frac{n_j}{n}, j = 1, \dots, J. \quad \text{With the density:} \quad d_j = \frac{f_j}{a_j}$$

Where d_j is the frequency density; n is the total number; f_j designates the frequency of j class. The area of the histogram is generally equal to the total frequency n , since the area of each rectangle is equal to the frequency of the class j .

To simplify the definition, Ayache [30] has designated the histogram of numbers in statistics as being the graphic representation of the numbers of each class. For Bele [31], the histogram is a method by which the distribution of evidence value data is presented. In the analysis of geological data, the histogram is used to check whether the distribution of the grades of ores or chemical elements in the samples and the boreholes is normal. Its analysis will make it possible to discover and correct errors called bimodal distribution or outliers to guarantee a good analysis of the data.

3.3.2 Cumulative Frequency Method

In descriptive statistics, the cumulative frequency F_j at the j class designates more simply as being the sum of the frequencies f_j or as being the ratio of the cumulative number N_j to the total number n . A distinction is made between increasing and decreasing cumulative frequencies. It is increasing when the proportion of observations, in the initial statistical series, is less than or equal to the value of the series with which the frequency is associated. It is decreasing otherwise. Its mathematical formula is written by:

In Geological Data Analysis, errors are also determined by the cumulative frequency curve of the grades. The principle

$$F_j = \frac{N_j}{n} = \sum_{k=1}^j f_k, j = 1, \dots, J. \quad N_j = \sum_{k=1}^j n_k, j = 1, \dots, J$$

of analysis of the curve is as follows: The smaller the distance between the various points of the cumulative frequency curve, the more the data resulting from these two points are coherent. On the contrary, a large distance between two points is synonymous with an error that must be corrected by deleting the data from the distant point in the database.

3.4 Performance indicators

The comparison of the statistical reports generated by each composite and the subsequent interpretation of the discrepancies between them and the actual values constitute the performance indicator analysis. The composite that shows the best ratio will be considered the composite with the best length. The important parameters to take into account in this statistical report are the variance, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, and mean.

3.4.1 The mean

The mean is a value that is used to summarize a group of data, often to better understand the overall value (magnitude and sign) of a data set. There are generally three categories of means. The arithmetic mean is calculated by adding all digits together and dividing by the number of digits used. The more complicated geometric mean with a more complex formula is obtained by multiplying all the values in a set of data and then taking the root of the sum equal to the number of values in that set of data. The quantum harmonic mean a is calculated by dividing the number of observations by the

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right) = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}$$

reciprocal of each number in the series. In our case, we use the arithmetic mean since it is statistically commonly used to measure the central tendency of data and in most scientific experiments. It is defined by the following formula:

Where:

\bar{x} = the mean of all the samples, therefore in our case the iron content; Σ = the sum of ...; n = the number of iron content values; i = iron content number and x = iron content value.

3.4.2 The variance

Statistical variance gives a measure of how well the data spread over the mean or expected value. Specifically, the variance measures the distance between each number in the set and the mean. The more spread out the data, the greater the variance from the mean. The advantage of variance is that it treats all deviations from the mean as the same, regardless of their direction. A disadvantage of variance, however, is that it gives more weight to outliers. These are the figures far from the mean. Squaring these numbers can skew the data. The variance is calculated by taking the mean of the squared deviations from the mean. A distinction is made between population variance in which data is collected from each member of a population and sample variance in which data is collected from a single sample. In our case, the variance of the population which represents the variance of the iron contents is defined by the formula:

Where:

σ^2 = variance of the iron content ; $\Sigma (X - \mu)^2$ = The sum of $(X - \mu)^2$ for all data or iron content points ; X = the individual

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\Sigma(X - \mu)^2}{N}$$

iron content ; μ = mean iron content ; N = number of iron concentrations in the population.

3.4.3 Standard deviation

The measure of variability in a data collection in relation to its mean is measured statistically by the standard deviation. It describes how the data is distributed over the mean value, on average, and how far away from the mean each value is. In general, values with a large standard deviation are dispersed from the mean, whereas those with a low standard deviation are concentrated close to the mean. The standard deviation is determined by taking the variance's square root. Although the variance provides a rough indication of the deviation, the standard deviation is more precise and provides precise distances from the mean. As for the case of the variance, the standard deviation of the population considered in our case is defined by the following formula:

Where:

σ = the standard deviation of the iron content ; $\Sigma (X - \mu)^2$ = The sum of $(X - \mu)^2$ for all data or iron content points ; X = the individual iron content ; μ = mean iron content ; N = number of iron concentrations in the population.

The standard deviation equals the mean if the value is one or 100%. Values less than one indicate that the standard

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma(X - \mu)^2}{N}}$$

deviation is less than the mean (typical), while values greater than one occurs when the standard deviation is greater than the mean.

3.4.4 Coefficient of variation

The coefficient of variation (CV) is a relative measure of variability which shows how much a standard deviation deviates from the mean. Even when the means of two sets of data are very different from one another, the coefficient of

$$CV = \frac{\sigma}{\mu}$$

variation, which measures the standard deviation in relation to the mean, can be used to compare the degree of variation between the two sets of data. The coefficient of variation demonstrates how variable a sample's results are in comparison to the population mean. Contrary to the standard deviation, which must always be viewed in relation to the data mean, the coefficient of variation offers a reasonably quick and easy method for contrasting several data series. Mathematically, the standard formula for the coefficient of variation is expressed as follows:

Where:

CV = coefficient of variation; σ = standard deviation; μ = mean. The higher the coefficient of variation, the greater the dispersion.

4. Results

4.1 Data collection and pre-processing

The maximum depths, elevations, azimuth values, and angles of dip of each borehole have been determined by analyzing the maps of the sections of each line of geological explorations. The sites of each borehole are shown on the geological map of the study region, which was geo-referenced in ArcGIS 10.8 mapping software, allowing the extraction of their coordinates. The values of the samples in these drill holes have been graded as a function of length, and the results have been obtained in the form of an image file in the exploratory sections. All of this data was entered into an Excel file, and then computations and small graphs were made to check the consistency of the data and to identify and fix input errors. The data was then filtered and rearranged to fit into the Surpac software's format for the COLLAR, SURVEY, and ASSAY tables. In total, data from 60 drill holes and 925 samples were collected. Tables 1, 2, and 3 below reflect a portion of these three tables.

Table 1: Table of the first five rows of the Collar table

hole_id	there	x	z	max_depth (m)	orebody
ZK0001	5248791.353	444191.474	1563.000	58.17	Fe1
ZK3E01	5248831.461	444026.022	1564.000	81.87	Fe1
ZK3W02	5248883.989	443964.218	1580.000	86.22	Fe1
ZK303	5248861.661	443996.718	1563.000	62.08	Fe1
ZK4W02	5248689.471	444354.622	1594.000	103.37	Be3

Table au 2: Table of the first five rows of the Survey table.

hole_id	Depth (m)	dip	azimuth
ZK0001	58.170	-75.000	195,000
ZK3E01	81.870	-50.000	35,000
ZK3W02	86.220	-50.000	35,000
ZK303	62.080	-50.000	35,000
ZK4W02	103.370	-75.000	217,000

Table 3: Table of the first five rows of the Assay table.

holde_id	depth_from (m)	depth_to (m)	sample length (m)	Fe (%)	orebody
ZK0001	2.100	4.100	2,000	0.000	Fe1
ZK0001	4.100	6.100	2,000	43.280	Fe1
ZK0001	6.100	8.100	2,000	27.730	Fe1
ZK0001	8.100	10.100	2,000	40,500	Fe1
ZK0001	10.100	12.100	2,000	31,390	Fe1

In these tables, holde_id represents the column of sample numbers, x represents longitudes, y represents latitudes, z represents elevations, depth and max_depth represent maximum depths and depths respectively, and Fe represents mean iron content. Sample lengths generally fall within the range of 0.5 meters to 2.5 meters although in some cases values below (up to 0.2 meters) or above (up to 6 meters) this range have been observed.

In table 3, the variance, the mean, the standard deviation, the coefficient of variation of the iron contents, and the mean lengths of the samples were calculated and represented by table 4 below.

Table 4: Statistical ratio of actual iron content values

number of samples	mean (%)	variance	standard deviation	coefficient of variation	mean length of samples.
925	29.7515805	254.964441	15.967606	0.53669719	1.81962162

In Table 4, it can be seen that the deviation between the variance and the mean of the iron contents is large and reaches a factor of more than 8. This means that the iron ore in the study area is very unevenly distributed or in other words its variability is great. The mean of this variability of iron contents concerning its mean is indicated by a standard deviation which is approximately 16 and its coefficient is 0.534.

4.2 Construction of composites and Data analysis

4.2.1 Data analysis for outlier checking or bimodal distribution

From, the Collar, Survey and Assay tables and with the menu database_open /new of the Surpac software, the geological database was established and audited. Then with the value of the mean length of the samples in table 4, a first composite was built to make a first statistical analysis to check the errors called bimodal distribution or outliers. These errors represent abnormal values of the iron contents which must be eliminated so as not to influence the analysis of the data. For this, with the Database_Analysis_Baisic-Statistic-windows menu, a graph of the histograms and the cumulative frequency curve represented by figure 3 below was established to observe the iron content in each sample.

Figure 3: Graph of the histograms and cumulative frequencies of the iron contents in the samples.

The principle states that the aberrant values or outliers must be represented by one or more isolated histograms or by histograms that are abnormally large in comparison to other groups of histograms, while for the cumulative frequency curve, they are represented by a large distance or an abnormal distance between two points on the curve. In Figure 3, the histograms represented by the color red have a normal distribution, and the blue points on the cumulative frequency curve have a normal distribution. This indicates that no outliers were found, and the data are valid.

4.2.2 Construction and statistical analysis of test composites

Considering composite lengths commonly used in ore resource reserve estimates [1, 5-18, 23, 24], previous composite length studies [26], and mean lengths from the samples of the study area, five composites were first constructed, represented graphically in the histogram and cumulative frequency, then their statistical reports were extracted. In the order to build the other test composites, the amplitude of the lengths was narrowed more around the lengths of the composites which showed values of mean iron content closer to the real mean iron content in table 4. In this logic the composites of length 0.5 meters and 1 meter having best respected this condition, an interval of 0.05 meters was chosen between each length to build a succession of composites from 0.5 meters to 1.1 meters. The amplitude was also reinforced around the mean length of the samples which is 1.82 meters. Finally, values that are a little far from this length were taken to see the influence of such a difference on the data. A total of thirty (30) composites were constructed and graphically analyzed. The graphical representations of the histograms and cumulative frequency curves of each of these composites are given in Figure 4. Their statistical reports were extracted in which the different values of mean iron content, variance, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation were recorded in Table 5.

Figure 4 shows very small variations in the shape of the curve of the cumulative frequencies of the composites of length between 0.5 meters and 2 meters. However, this variation is more striking at the level of the composites of lengths of 5 and 10 meters. This means that the number of samples taken into account in these composites of lengths 5 and 10 meters is very low and this could have an influence on the estimation of iron resource reserves in the Timulike zone. These graphs also show the decreasing evolution of the number of samples taken into account by each composite from more than 2500 samples to less than 300 samples. Remember that 2500 is an extremely high number and 300 an extremely low number compared to the real number

Fig. 4: Graphical representation of the iron content histograms of the thirty (30) test composites.

The composites column in Table 5 shows the name assigned to each composite in which the number before the prefix "compo" designates the length of this composite in meters. The other names "real value", "mean length (1.82)", and "compo_2.23 (add 0.5)" respectively denote the actual value in the sample data, the composite of the mean length of the samples, and the composite with the addition of 0.5 meters on the mean length samples by the method proposed above. From this table 5, graphs of histograms of the mean iron contents produced by each composite as well as those of their variance, their standard deviation, and their coefficient of variation were constructed for better observation. These graphs are represented by Figures 5-9.

Table 5: Statistical report of the different test composites.

composite	numbers of sam- ples	mean (%)	variance	standard devia- tion	coefficient of varia- tion
compo_0.5	3504	29.82536	269.849667	16.427102	0.550776
compo_0.55	3197	29.73073	269.069334	16.403333	0.55173
compo_0.6	2936	29.72847	267.851283	16.366163	0.550522
compo_0.65	2727	29.596887	267.966134	16.369671	0.553088
compo_0.7	2530	29.644439	267.332092	16.350293	0.551547
compo_0.75	2374	29.554349	266.15621	16.314295	0.55201
compo_0.8	2224	29.563481	265.773155	16.302551	0.551442
compo_0.85	2098	29.526253	265.061266	16.280702	0.551398
compo_0.9	1989	29.448596	266.149559	16.314091	0.553985
compo_0.95	1892	29.374188	264.613527	16.266946	0.553784
compo_1	1796	29.432564	264.591084	16.266256	0.552662
compo_1.05	1721	29.296284	263.630147	16.236691	0.554224
compo_1.1	1641	29.31955	264.118931	16.251736	0.554297
compo_1.2	1516	29.175152	261.701465	16.17719	0.554485
compo_1.3	1405	29.144391	260.533498	16.14105	0.55383
real-value	925	29.7515805	254.964441	15.967606	0.53669719
compo_1.4	1309	29.057277	260.453547	16.138573	0.555406
compo_1.5	1229	29.031165	259.025378	16.094265	0.554379
compo_1.6	1157	28.886251	258.120055	16.066115	0.556186
compo_1.65	1125	28.897052	257.028594	16.032111	0.554801
compo_1.7	1085	29.016222	255.299208	15.978085	0.55066
comp_1.75	1058	28.956734	254.392498	15.949686	0.550811
compo_1.8	1037	28.785482	254.514261	15.953503	0.55422
mean length (1.82)	1029	28.713419	255.750919	15.992214	0.55696
comp_1.85	1009	28.771489	255.801902	15.993808	0.555891
compo_1.9	990	28.662455	253.73844	15.929169	0.55575
component_1.95	966	28.628412	253.158841	15.910966	0.555775
compo_2	942	28.742636	254.482998	15.952523	0.555013
compo_2.23 (add 0.5)	825	28.318572	251.124082	15.846895	0.559594
compo_5	246	26.901702	189.275838	13.757756	0.511408
compo_10	246	26.901702	189.275838	13.757756	0.511408

Figures 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9 show the histograms of the value of the number of samples considered (figure 5), of the mean of the iron contents (figure 6), of the variance of these contents (figure 7), their standard deviation (figure 8) and their coefficient of variation (figure 9) in each composite compared to those of the real data present in the samples in red color and those of the composite constructed with the mean length of the samples in green color. In these different figures we can see that according to the histograms around the real values, the composites are divided into three groups which are: the group of composites of small lengths, the group of composites with lengths around the mean length samples, and the long length composites group.

Fig. 5: Graphical representation of sample number histograms.

In figure 5, a gradual decreasing variation in the number of samples considered in the composites is observed from the smallest lengths of composites to the long lengths. In addition to figure 5 and compared to the actual number of samples, in table 5 this number is on the one hand, approximately multiplied by four for the short-length composites which is an extremely high figure, on the other hand, it is divided by three for long composites which is also a very low figure. An ore resource reserve estimate considering such sample numbers very far from reality will most likely provide erroneous results. On the other hand, the composites with lengths oscillating around the mean length of the samples take into account several samples closer to the real number of samples. Figure 5 and Table 5 show that composites with lengths very far from the mean length of the samples could overestimate or underestimate the ore resources.

In Figure 6 and Table 5, the mean iron contents in the actual data are higher than the mean iron contents in all the

Fig. 6: Graphical representation of histograms of average iron levels.

composites. The composites in the short-length group show mean iron content in the range of 29.5% to 30% which is closer to the actual content than the others. The group of composites with lengths around the mean length of the samples in green show iron contents in the range of 28.5% to 29.5% which is acceptable compared to the mean contents in the real data. The third group of long-length composites (5 and 10 meters) shows grades below 27%, which is rather far behind all the others. Figure 6 shows the proportionality between the small composite lengths and the mean iron contents in the real data is closer.

Fig. 7: Graphic representation of histograms of iron content variances.

Fig. 8: Graphic representation of the histograms of the standard deviations of the iron contents.

In figures 7, 8, and in table 5, the variance and the standard deviation of the iron contents in the composites having lengths around the length of the samples are in the same value interval as the true variance and the actual standard deviation. For very long composites, the value of these parameters is lower. The group of short-length composites, on the other hand, has values of variances and standard deviations slightly higher than the real values. This means that the iron contents are more spread out in these short-length composites than the others and also that the distances between these contents and their mean are greater than those in the real data. In longer composite lengths, this distance is shorter. This also means that the distribution of iron contents around their mean and the distance between these two in the composites having lengths around the mean length of the samples is closer to reality than the other two.

Fig. 9: Graphical representation of the histograms of the coefficients of variation of the iron contents.

In the first scenario, as shown in Figure 9 and Table 5, the iron content's coefficient of variation is lower in the real data than it is in the composites with short lengths and those with lengths that oscillate around the samples' length. In contrast, this coefficient is higher in the second instance compared to the composites of large lengths. This indicates that the iron contents' degree of variation in the composites of the first case is greater than the iron contents' degree of variation in the real data. It is the contrary in the composites of the second situation. This is likely due to the fact that in lengthy composites, where the number of samples is divided by 3, fewer samples are included in the calculations than

in the others. Additionally, the iron content variability in short-length composites is lower than that in composites with lengths that are similar to the length of the samples.

4.2.3 Analysis of the difference between the actual values and the values in the composites

The calculation of the difference between the actual statistical parameters of the iron content contained in Table 4 and the statistical parameters obtained by each composite contained in Table 5 was carried out and the numerical results were recorded in Table 6. The graphs and histograms of these differences in values of table 6 are represented by figures 10, 11, 12, 13, and 14. This makes it possible to observe and compare in a more detailed and precise manner these parameters between them, especially since in this case a parameter is better when its value is closer to zero or otherwise when its histogram bar is closer to the abscissa axis of ordinate equal to zero. It is lower than the corresponding real parameter when the difference result is negative or when its histogram bar is reversed and it is higher otherwise.

Table 6: Result of differences between the real statistical parameters and the statistical parameters of the composites

composite	The real mean of Fe	Real-variance	Real Standard Deviation	Real Coefficient Variation	Real samples number
	-	-	-	-	-
	Composite mean Fe	composite-variance	Composite Standard Deviation	Composite Coefficient variation	Composite samples number
compo_0.5	-0.0737795	-14.885226	-0.459496	-0.0140788	-2579
compo_0.55	0.02085054	-14.104893	-0.435727	-0.0150328	-2272
compo_0.6	0.02311054	-12.886842	-0.398557	-0.0138248	-2011
compo_0.65	0.15469354	-13.001693	-0.402065	-0.0163908	-1802
compo_0.7	0.10714154	-12.367651	-0.382687	-0.0148498	-1605
compo_0.75	0.19723154	-11.191769	-0.346689	-0.0153128	-1449
compo_0.8	0.18809954	-10.808714	-0.334945	-0.0147448	-1299
compo_0.85	0.22532754	-10.096825	-0.313096	-0.0147008	-1173
compo_0.9	0.30298454	-11.185118	-0.346485	-0.0172878	-1064
compo_0.95	0.37739254	-9.6490862	-0.29934	-0.0170868	-967
compo_1	0.31901654	-9.6266432	-0.29865	-0.0159648	-871
compo_1.05	0.45529654	-8.6657062	-0.269085	-0.0175268	-796
compo_1.1	0.43203054	-9.1544902	-0.28413	-0.0175998	-716
compo_1.2	0.57642854	-6.7370242	-0.209584	-0.0177878	-591
compo_1.3	0.60718954	-5.5690572	-0.173444	-0.0171328	-480
real-value	0	0	0	0	0
compo_1.4	0.69430354	-5.4891062	-0.170967	-0.0187088	-384
compo_1.5	0.72041554	-4.0609372	-0.126659	-0.0176818	-304
compo_1.6	0.86532954	-3.1556142	-0.098509	-0.0194888	-232
compo_1.65	0.85452854	-2.0641532	-0.064505	-0.0181038	-200
compo_1.7	0.73535854	-0.3347672	-0.010479	-0.0139628	-160
compo_1.75	0.79484654	0.57194284	0.01791998	-0.0141138	-133
compo_1.8	0.96609854	0.45017984	0.01410298	-0.0175228	-112
mean length	1.03816154	-0.7864782	-0.024608	-0.0202628	-104

comp_1.85	0.98009154	-0.8374612	-0.026202	-0.0191938	-84
compo_1.9	1.08912554	1.22600084	0.03843698	-0.0190528	-65
component_1.95	1.12316854	1.80559984	0.05663998	-0.0190778	-41
compo_2	1.00894454	0.48144284	0.01508298	-0.0183158	-17
compo_2.23 (add 0.5)	1.43300854	3.84035884	0.12071098	-0.0228968	100
compo_5	2.84987854	65.6886028	2.20984998	0.02528919	679
compo_10	2.84987854	65.6886028	2.20984998	0.02528919	679

The major objective in this section is to see how close each result is to zero and how close each histogram bar is to the abscissa axis. Table 6 and figures 10, 11, 12, 13, and 14 are the respective derivatives of Table 5 and figures 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9. Since the outcome of this difference is 0, we can observe on each graph that the portion corresponding to the true value is empty. The value of the statistical parameter relating to a result is closer to the true value the closer a bar is to the abscissa axis or the smaller the absolute value of its result. The composite that corresponds to this parameter is therefore better.

Fig. 10: Graphic representation of the histograms of the difference between the actual sample number and the sample number in the composites.

The composites in figure 10 with lengths that are near to the mean length of the samples, more specifically the composites with lengths of 2 meters, 1.95 meters, and 1.9 meters, are those that are closest to the abscissa axis. This indicates that these composites will produce results in the estimation and computation of mineral resource reserves that are more realistic given the sample under consideration. Table 6 shows that the composite of length 2 meters, which has 17 less samples than the actual samples, performs much better than the other two. On the other hand, composites of short length are not recommended in this field, more particularly the composite of length 0.5 meters which take into account 2579 samples more than the number of real samples.

Fig. 11: Graphic representation of the histograms of the difference between the actual average iron content and the average iron contents in the composites.

The composites with long lengths (5 and 10 meters) in figure 11 exhibit greater percentage variations of about 3%, which is worse than the other composites. That these composites' mean iron content is less accurate than that of other composites. In contrast, short-length composites perform well in this register, particularly the 0.55-meter composite, which has a mean iron content difference of about 0.02%, as shown in Table 6, which is approximately equivalent to the mean iron content in the real data. Except for the composites of lengths 1.9 meters and 1.95 meters, which exhibit values somewhat higher than 1%, the length composites around the mean length of the samples differ in iron content by an order of 0.5% to 1%.

The variances and standard deviations of the shortest lengths of composites gradually increase from the real values to the longest lengths, as shown in Figures 12 and 13, which appear to be nearly identical. These plots show that, with the exception of the length of 1.95 meters, which yielded results of 1.8 for the variance and 0.05 for the standard deviation, composites with lengths close to the mean length of the samples have the smallest variance and standard deviation differences, in the order of 0.3 to 1 for variance and 0.01 to 0.02 for standard deviation. They are therefore better when these two statistical parameters are taken into consideration. The composite with a length of 1.7 meters in Table 6 performs the best in these two registers when combined, with absolute values of 0.33 for variance and 0.01 for standard deviation. The composites with a length of 1.8 meters and 2 meters are next, with values of 0.45 and 0.48 for variance and 0.014 and 0.015 for standard deviation, respectively.

Fig. 12: Graphic representation of the histograms of the difference between the real variances of the iron contents and the variances of the iron contents in the composites.

Fig. 13: Graphic representation of the histograms of the difference between the actual standard deviation of the iron contents and the standard deviations of the iron contents in the composites.

Fig. 14: Graphic representation of the histograms of the difference between the actual coefficient of variation of the iron contents and the coefficients of variation of the iron contents in the composites.

Figure 14 shows that in terms of coefficient of variation, the composites of long lengths have the greatest difference, therefore worse results. This figure also shows that all the bars on mean are far from the abscissa axis.

5. Discussion

5.1 Long-length composites (5 meters and 10 meters)

The number of samples considered in the composites of great length is equal to 246 which is three times lower compared to the actual number of samples (925 samples) which demonstrates an omission of more than half of all the original drilling data. These composites do not reflect the reality on the ground and cannot represent these data in the estimation and calculation of ore reserves as recalled by Lee [6]. A central tendency of the iron contents reduced by more than 2.5% and being the weakest of the composite groups means that the composites of great lengths will have a greater influence on the quality of the ore in useful element and consequently on the precision of the results. estimation compared to other composites in the study area. These results prove that these composites will underestimate the resource reserves of the ore of the study area and are not advised for the calculation of the resource reserves in the Timulike iron deposit. This is also explained by the weak distribution (13.75) and the weak degree of variation (0.51) of the iron contents around the mean in comparison with the real data (respectively 15.96 and 0.54, see table 5 and 6 and figures 5-14). The mineral distribution in the Timulike iron deposit being discontinuous in nature combined with the results obtained also correlate with the version of Moharaj [26] who believes that long-length composites would be more suitable for estimating deposits of continuous mineral distribution.

5.2 Short-length composites

The mean iron content displayed in the short-length composites, which is 29.73% for 0.55 meters in length, is the closest to the mean real content, which is 29.75%, i.e., a difference of only 0.02% (tables 5 and 6). On the other hand, as in the previous case, the number of samples considered in these composites (2374 samples for 0.5 meters of composite length, table 5) being nearly four times greater than the actual number of samples shows an increase beyond the reality of the original drilling data (table 5 and 6, figures 5 and 10). This is also not acceptable in terms of estimating reserve resources since they will be much more likely to overestimate ore resources. They are therefore not representative of Lee [6] bore-hole data. Moreover, the distribution of the iron contents around their mean as well as the distance between them in these composites of short lengths is greater and further from the real data than in the composites which have lengths oscillating around the length of the samples. In addition, although the degree of variation of the contents in the composites of short length is lower than that of the composites having lengths around the mean length of the samples, the difference between the values is very small (of the order of 0.0001, table 5 and 6), compared to the variance and the

standard deviation where the difference in deviation is greater (up to 14 for the variance and 0.4 for the standard deviation, table 6 and figure 12 and 13). Therefore, in view of all presented, these short-length composites are not as advisable for estimating Timulike 's resource reserves closer to drill hole data.

5.3 Length composites around the mean length of the samples

With better results in terms of the number of samples considered (942 for 2 meters against 925 in reality), variance and standard deviation (respectively 255.3 and 15.98 for 1.7 meters against 254.96 and 15.967 in reality), and very low coefficients of variation compared to the composites of short length and in the real data (0.550522 for 0.6 meters, 0.55066 for 1.7 meters, 0.536697 in reality), It is obvious that the composites built with lengths distributed around the mean length samples are more advisable in the estimation and calculation of the reserves of the study area. Toka ^[2] and Mello ^[25] also based themselves on this conclusion to choose the length of their composite. Moreover, which composite length can be chosen among these to have estimation results closer to reality? To solve this problem, table 7 below extracted from table 6 displays the proportions of the difference between the statistical parameters of composites with the real statistical parameters to observe which one has the best ratio. Here, only composites with better statistical outcome ratios are considered.

Table 7: Proportion of the difference between the actual statistical parameters and the statistical parameters of the composites having lengths around the mean.

composite	Numbers of samples difference	Mean Difference (%)	Variance difference	Standard deviation deference	Coefficient of variation difference
compo_1.7	160	0.73535854	0.33476716	0.01047902	0.01396281
compo_1.75	133	0.79484654	0.57194284	0.01791998	0.01411381
compo_1.8	112	0.96609854	0.45017984	0.01410298	0.01752281
mean length	104	1.03816154	0.78647816	0.02460802	0.02026281
compo_1.85	84	0.98009154	0.83746116	0.02620202	0.01919381
compo_1.9	65	1.08912554	1.22600084	0.03843698	0.01905281
compo_1.95	41	1.12316854	1.80559984	0.05663998	0.01907781
compo_2	17	1.00894454	0.48144284	0.01508298	0.01831581

The principle is that as the red bar of a cell is short, the composite corresponding to this cell has the best ratio. According to this table 7, the composite with the best value ratio is the one with a length of **2 meters**. So, this length is more advisable for estimating and calculating iron ore resource reserves in the Timulike area.

6. Conclusion

In summary, composite length is a parameter that influences the accuracy of ore resource reserve estimation with computer software such as Surpac. We compared the statistical results of thirty composites of different lengths for the correct choice of this length in the Timulike iron deposit. Analysis has shown that long-length composites will produce results that are three times more underestimated than they are in reality. This is due to variability and the number of samples considered lower. Conversely, composites of lengths that are too small will overestimate the reserves of iron resources four times. On the other hand, this is due to greater variability and a greater number of samples. Finally, the composites, which have lengths around the mean length of the samples, showed variabilities closer to reality. This means that these composites are better advised to have an optimal and precise result in the estimation and calculation of mineralized resource reserves of the Timulike iron ore type in other regions. Finally, the composite with a length of 2 meters that showed the best result ratio was chosen for the estimation of the Timulike iron deposits.

In addition, an in-depth study in which we will proceed directly to an estimate and a calculation of the resource reserves with each length of composite is also a case to be considered in the future. In this context, analyzing estimation errors

using linear regression, mean squared error, or other methods will allow us to judge the precision of the estimation results produced by each composite.

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